

Strengthening Children's Reading Habits through Home-Based Learning Corners: A Scalable Model by Aasaman Nepal

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Abstract

A recent observation revealed that a majority of school-aged children are not engaging in reading or academic activities at home, often spending time playing before and after school and showing limited respect for parental guidance. This lack of structured study time has contributed to declining learning outcomes. In response, Aasaman Nepal initiated a home-based Learning Corner intervention to promote regular reading habits and improve academic discipline among Children.

The Home based Learning Corner provides a dedicated and safe space for children to study within their own homes, encouraging consistent engagement with education beyond school hours. This initiative supports families in creating the corner using locally available resources, while also providing essential learning and reading materials. Parental engagement has been crucial. It makes parents more responsible toward child right protection and positive caring of the child as well. The teachers and School Management Committee (SMC) members mobilized for door-to-door visits to monitor progress and provide support and an encouragement as well. Additionally, orientations on positive parenting are conducted with mothers' groups to reinforce the importance of parental support and conversation with their children in the Learning process.

Feedback from children and parents has been collected through interviews and community meetings, revealing strong appreciation for the Learning Corner approach. Children have shown increased focus, improved study routines, and a growing interest in reading. Parents have become more engaged in their children's education, creating a more friendly and respectful home learning culture.

Expected outcomes include a sustained and enriching learning environment at home, stronger reading habits contributing to lifelong skills, improved academic performance, enhanced parent-child relationships, and a heightened sense of responsibility among students. This community-supported and resource-efficient model shows strong potential for scaling up across similar contexts to address foundational learning gaps in Madhesh.

Keywords: Home-based Learning, Learning Corner, Reading Habit, Parental Engagement, Community- Based Education